

**D5.6 Up to 10 short videos to promote the EU FarmBook
to various end-users**

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

TASK 5.4

Summary

This document records the finalisation of the short videos made in **Task 5.4** (*Promote and enhance the use of EUREKA project outputs*). A total of 13 videos were made for public dissemination and are all available via Youtube:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdIdXENhLoY7OetQ1UHul3A>

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	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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History of Changes

Date	Changes
12 August 2022	New Section 2 (Persona videos) inserted with additional information on specific development of the persona videos.
	Section 3 (List of videos) restructured and updated to include supplementary information on each video. This includes purpose, and methodology, plus duration, video language and subtitles. Background information on the concept of the video and issues associated with video creation are also included where appropriate.
	New Section 4 (Conclusions) inserted

1. Introduction and Approach

The aim of **Task 5.4** was to implement the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of EUREKA by promoting and enhancing the use of outputs of the EUREKA project. One specific activity proposed in the project's Description of Action was the preparation of:

“...up to 5 short-streaming videos will be produced for each of the main end-user categories (up to 10 in total) - one general introductory video, plus up to 4 contrasting use cases that illustrate the full scope and diversity of the content of the FarmBook”.

This document records the finalisation of these videos. A total of **13 videos** were made for public dissemination consisting of:

- **Two introductory videos** that explain the background, purpose, and context of the EUREKA project;
- **One step-by-step guide** to the uploading of ‘knowledge objects’ which is intended to accompany the Upload Manual (not a deliverable) prepared in WP4;
- **Five ‘persona’ videos** intended to “bring to life” a contrasting selection of the personas and knowledge journeys developed in WP2 for helping understand the knowledge requirements of farmers, foresters, and advisors across the EU;
- **Five keynote presentations** from the Final Outreach Event organised on Tuesday, 29 March 2022.

All videos are available via Youtube:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdIdXENhLoY7OetQ1UHul3A>

The titles, short descriptions, potential end-users, individual Youtube links, the purpose, and methodology are listed in 13 tables in Section 3.

2. Persona videos

The five short ‘persona’ videos were produced by LAAS and aimed to “bring to life” the following personas from WP2:

- Claudia (a young farmer from Germany)
- Hans (a public forestry advisor from The Netherlands)
- Edganear-retirement arable farmer from Lithuania)
- Agnetha (a livestock advisor from Sweden), and
- Ignacio (a forest manager from Spain).

The scripts were initially conceived and drafted by RAU with the intention that the videos would be filmed in different locations across Europe. However, the covid crisis did not permit this and all 5 videos were filmed in Lithuania using carefully selected locations (to create the impression of contrasting geographical locations) and the staff of LAAS as actors.

After post-production the videos were uploaded on Youtube and subtitled in English, plus all of the project partner’s national languages (DE, DK, EE, ES, EL, FR, HU, IT, LT, NL, PL, RO, SI). The translated subtitles were created using the auto-translation function available in Youtube and were checked / corrected by relevant partners before being published.

3. List of videos

No.1	
Title	H2020 EUREKA Project Presentation
Type of video	Introductory video
Main purpose of the video	To introduce the EUREKA project to all potential users.
Methodology	Short animated video. Duration of the video - 2 min. 10 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles also available in English, Spanish, Dutch, Slovenian, Hungarian, and German. The video introduces the purpose of the EUREKA project and what practical knowledge it contains for farmers or other participants in the agriculture sector.
Short description	A brief introduction to the EUREKA project.
Potential end-users	Intended for all potential end-users.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/qOr8nXN_xMQ
Dissemination channels	Youtube channel, Eureka website

No.2	
Title	Handing over from EURAKNOS to EUREKA
Type of video	Introductory video
Main purpose of the video	To introduce and explain main differences between sister-projects EURAKNOS and EUREKA and invite listeners to contribute to the project results on a platform developed by the EUREKA project.
Methodology	Short animated video. Duration of the video is 3 min. 31 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles in English also. All animated videos use the same voice-over and drawing style in order to be linked and recognized as EUREKA products. Scenario of this video focuses on presenting main results of EURAKNOS (Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks, Policy brief, Prototype of the online agricultural platform) and how the first functional version of an easily searchable digital knowledge reservoir was constructed by EUREKA experts based on the knowledge and blueprints from the EURAKNOS project.
Short description	An explanation of the relationship between the EURAKNOS and EUREKA projects, including how EUREKA is built upon the work of EURAKNOS.

Potential end-users	Intended primarily for the multi-actor project community ¹ .
Video Link	https://youtu.be/SIId7Fjt9xU
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.3	
Title	Uploading 'knowledge objects' in the (pilot) EU FarmBook
Type of video	Step-by-step guide
Main purpose of the video	To instruct project managers and other users how to upload knowledge objects to EU Farmbook
Methodology	Duration of the video is 5 min. 42 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles in English also. The video captures real images of the platform and gives a step-by-step guide on how to upload data to EU FarmBook. The idea behind this video is that visualized instructions in today's world are more attractive than written ones. As data upload to the system is not an easy process, it was assumed that a tutorial video on the technical process of uploading of knowledge objects to the EU FarmBook will be extremely useful.
Short description	A step-by-step guide to the uploading of 'knowledge objects' to the (pilot) EU FarmBook.
Potential end-users	Intended primarily for the multi-actor project community.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/acDPm5riohs
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.4	
Title	EUREKA personas: Claudia
Type of video	'Persona' videos
Main purpose of the video	To illustrate the practical potential of EU FarmBook platform

¹ The multi-actor project community, including the full range of participants in past and present H2020 multi-actor projects (this inevitably includes some overlap with other groups of end-users)

Methodology	<p>Short animated video. Duration of the video is 2 min. 58 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles in the following languages: English, Danish, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Polish, Lithuanian, Romanian, Slovenian and Spanish.</p> <p>All 'Persona' video scripts were initially conceived and drafted by RAU with the intention that the videos would be filmed in different locations across Europe. However, the Covid crisis did not permit this and all 5 videos were filmed in Lithuania. Filming, editing, acting, set preparation, location scouting, editing of animation, voice-over ordering, and other activities related to the process of video making were carried out by LAAS. The same voice-over and animation are used in all 5 videos as it is in fully animated videos.</p>
Short description	<p>Claudia is a young farmer who lives with her parents on their fruit farm in Germany where she has spent her entire life. This short video shows her 'knowledge journey' towards the end of her time at university and how the EU FarmBook could potentially help her joining the family business.</p>
Potential end-users	<p>Intended for all potential end-users.</p>
Video Link	<p>https://youtu.be/VrqM1GUYcRw</p>
Dissemination channel	<p>Youtube channel</p>

No.5	
Title	EUREKA personas: Hans
Type of video	'Persona' videos
Main purpose of the video	To illustrate the practical potential of EU FarmBook platform
Methodology	<p>Short animated video. Duration of the video is 2 min. 16 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles in the following languages: English, Danish, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Polish, Lithuanian, Romanian, Slovenian and Spanish.</p> <p>All 'Persona' video scripts were initially conceived and drafted by RAU with the intention that the videos would be filmed in different locations across Europe. However, the Covid crisis did not permit this and all 5 videos were filmed in Lithuania. Filming, editing, acting, set preparation, location scouting, animation editing, voice-over ordering, and other activities related to the process of video making were carried out by LAAS. The same voice-over and animation are used in all 5 videos as it is in fully animated videos.</p>
Short description	<p>Hans is a 35-year-old public forestry advisor from the Netherlands. He has always been fascinated by nature and thinks that healthy forests are key in helping to deal with climate change. This short video explores how the EU</p>

	FarmBook could help him solve problems he encounters in his day-to-day work.
Potential end-users	Intended for all potential end-users.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/NRcqV06i0eA
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.6	
Title	EUREKA personas: Edgars
Type of video	'Persona' videos
Main purpose of the video	To illustrate the practical potential of EU FarmBook platform
Methodology	<p>Short animated video. Duration of the video is 2 min. 06 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles added in the following languages: English, Danish, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Polish, Lithuanian, Romanian, Slovenian and Spanish.</p> <p>All 'Persona' video scripts were initially conceived and drafted by RAU with the intention that the videos would be filmed in different locations across Europe. However, the Covid crisis did not permit this and all 5 videos were filmed in Lithuania. Filming, editing, acting, set preparation, location scouting, animation editing, voice-over ordering, and other activities related to the process of video making were carried out by LAAS. The same voice-over and animation are used in all 5 videos as it is in fully animated videos.</p>
Short description	Edgars is an experienced arable farmer who realises that he needs to think about retiring. However, he do not feel ready and asks for guidance to help him make the right decision. This short video explains how the EU FarmBook could help Edgars' advisor find an innovative solution for the challenges of generational renewal and for the installation of a young farmer or another new entrant into his farm business.
Potential end-users	Intended for all potential end-users.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/KGmraN_Kag0
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.7	
Title	EUREKA personas: Agnetha
Type of video	'Persona' videos
Main purpose of the video	To illustrate the practical potential of EU FarmBook platform
Methodology	<p>Short animated video. Duration of the video is 1 min. 45 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles added in the following languages: English, Danish, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Polish, Lithuanian, Romanian, Slovenian and Spanish.</p> <p>All 'Persona' video scripts were initially conceived and drafted by RAU with the intention that the videos would be filmed in different locations across Europe. However, the Covid crisis did not permit this and all 5 videos were filmed in Lithuania. Filming, editing, acting, set preparation, location scouting, animation editing, voice-over ordering, and other activities related to the process of video making were carried out by LAAS. The same voice-over and animation are used in all 5 videos as it is in fully animated videos.</p>
Short description	Agnetha is a 34-year-old livestock advisor from Sweden. She lives on a small holding with her husband and son. Agnetha gets a phone call from one of her farming clients who has a problem with his chickens pecking each other. This short video records Agnetha's visit to the poultry farm and illustrates how she could use the EU FarmBook to help solve the farmer's problem.
Potential end-users	Intended for all potential end-users.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/2uRdF-AwB60
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.8	
Title	EUREKA personas: Ignacio
Type of video	'Persona' videos
Main purpose of the video	To illustrate the practical potential of EU FarmBook platform
Methodology	<p>Short animated video. Duration of the video is 2 min. 17 sec. This video is narrated in English with subtitles added in the following languages: English, Danish, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Polish, Lithuanian, Romanian, Slovenian and Spanish.</p> <p>All 'Persona' video scripts were initially conceived and drafted by RAU with the intention that the videos would be filmed in different locations across</p>

	Europe. However, the Covid crisis did not permit this and all 5 videos were filmed in Lithuania. Filming, editing, acting, set preparation, location scouting, animation editing, voice-over ordering, and other activities related to the process of video making were carried out by LAAS. The same voice-over and animation are used in all 5 videos as it is in fully animated videos.
Short description	Ignacio is an experienced forest manager from Spain. He is very forward-thinking and this short video presents his potential use of the EU FarmBook for finding information on the latest innovations of digital forest management.
Potential end-users	Intended for all potential end-users.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/dChFnfMBoU
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.9	
Title	EUREKA! Making the EU FarmBook a reality (1)
Type of video	Keynote presentations
Main purpose of the video	To present the concept of the EU FarmBook
Methodology	Duration of the video is 34 min. 39 sec. This video is spoken in English with subtitles in English too. The video is part of the Final Outreach Event of EUREKA on Tuesday, 29 March 2022. The idea behind this video is to present the concept of EU FarmBook demonstrating how this idea was developed and why and to present the view of the team of EUREKA about EU FarmBook.
Short description	Final Outreach Event of EUREKA: Tuesday, 29 March 2022 Session 1: The EU FarmBook Story So-far: Design, Achievements, and Lessons Learned Opening presentation on the EU FarmBook "story" so-far by Project Coordinator, Pieter Spanoghe, University of Ghent. How did we get here and what is the EU FarmBook?
Potential end-users	Intended for the multi-actor project community, policy-makers/decision-takers and knowledge intermediaries to farmers and foresters.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/gTuQUqf5JLo
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.10	
Title	EUREKA! Making the EU FarmBook a reality (2)
Type of video	Keynote presentations
Main purpose of the video	To present the EU FarmBook platform and explain its origin
Methodology	<p>Duration of the video is 5 min. 18 sec. This video is spoken in English with subtitles in English too. The video is part of the Final Outreach Event of EUREKA on Tuesday, 29 March 2022.</p> <p>The idea behind this video is to present EU FarmBook and give some background information on why some solutions were achieved and what feedback from potential end-users was received.</p>
Short description	<p>Final Outreach Event of EUREKA: Tuesday, 29 March 2022</p> <p>Session 1: The EU FarmBook Story So-far: Design, Achievements and Lessons Learned</p> <p>A short introduction to the "look and feel" of the pilot EU FarmBook by Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Leap Forward Group.</p>
Potential end-users	Intended for the multi-actor project community, policy-makers, and knowledge intermediaries to farmers and foresters.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/aAjPz0jqV-w
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.11	
Title	EUREKA! Making the EU FarmBook a reality (3)
Type of video	Keynote presentations
Main purpose of the video	To demonstrate EU FarmBook functionality
Methodology	<p>Duration of the video is 18 min. 43 sec. This video is spoken in English with subtitles in English too. The video is part of the Final Outreach Event of EUREKA on Tuesday, 29 March 2022.</p> <p>The idea behind this video is to present the front-end of the EU FarmBook platform and its main functions and give some background information on how and why some solutions were arrived at.</p>
Short description	<p>Final Outreach Event of EUREKA: Tuesday, 29 March 2022</p> <p>Session 2: Getting 'Hands-on' with the Pilot EU FarmBook</p>

	A more in-depth look at features and functionalities of the pilot EU FarmBook by Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Leap Forward Group.
Potential end-users	Intended for the multi-actor project community, policy-makers, and knowledge intermediaries to farmers and foresters.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/4ZNYdWtuWBo
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.12	
Title	EUREKA! Making the EU FarmBook a reality (4)
Type of video	Keynote presentations
Main purpose of the video	To demonstrate how FAIR principles are applied to EU FarmBook
Methodology	<p>Duration of the video is 30 min. 30 sec. This video is spoken in English. The video is part of the Final Outreach Event of EUREKA on Tuesday, 29 March 2022.</p> <p>The FAIR principle is a very important issue in Multi-actor projects. The idea of this video is to reveal how EUREKA complies with it.</p>
Short description	<p>Final Outreach Event of EUREKA: Tuesday, 29 March 2022</p> <p>Session 2: Getting 'Hands-on' with the Pilot EU FarmBook</p> <p>What lies beneath the EU FarmBook? A detailed look at the approach of EUREKA to FAIR data by Hercules Panoutsopoulos, Agricultural University of Athens and a preview of the process of contributing to EU FarmBook via the upload form (more details here: https://youtu.be/acDPm5riohts) are presented in the video.</p>
Potential end-users	Intended for the multi-actor project community, policy-makers, and knowledge intermediaries to farmers and foresters with a specific interest in the role of the EU FarmBook in strengthening the AKIS.
Video Link	https://youtu.be/kVEioGI9Z5g
Dissemination channel	Youtube channel

No.13	
Title	EUREKA! Making the EU FarmBook a reality (5)
Type of video	Keynote presentations
Main purpose of the video	To present future perspective of EU FarmBook
Methodology	Duration of the video is 16 min. 31 sec. This video is spoken in English with subtitles in English too. The video is part of the Final Outreach Event of EUREKA on Tuesday, 29 March 2022. This is the final video of the project EUREKA. The idea behind this video is to show what future plans for developing and improving EU FarmBook are.
Short description	Final Outreach Event of EUREKA: Tuesday, 29 March 2022 Session 3: Key Opportunities and Challenges for the Future of the EU FarmBook An overview of a new 7-year Horizon Europe project, including transition and opportunities to get involved by the Project Co-ordinator, Pieter Spanoghe, University of Ghent.
Potential end-users	Intended for the multi-actor project community, policy-makers and knowledge intermediaries to farmers and foresters.
Video Link	To present future perspective of EU FarmBook
Dissemination channel	Duration of the video is 16 min. 31 sec. This video is dubbed in English, subtitles are in English too. The video is part of Final Outreach Event of EUREKA on Tuesday, 29 March 2022. This is the final video of the project EUREKA. The idea behind this video is to show what future plans for developing and improving EU FarmBook are.

4. Conclusions

It was originally proposed to produce “up to 10” short streaming videos and a total of 13 were actually uploaded to Youtube. Of these, it is acknowledged that 7 are likely to be most relevant to potential end-users of the EUREKA project:

- Video nr.1 explaining the general background and purpose, and context of the EUREKA project;
- Video nr.3 providing step-by-step guidance to the uploading of ‘knowledge objects’;
- Videos nr. 4-8 that “bring to life” a contrasting selection of the end-user ‘personas’.

Although at the time of writing the number of ‘views’ for the ‘persona’ videos are relatively small (25-55 per video), the potential for gaining more views is illustrated by video nr.1 which has well-over 1,000 views.

Most important to note is the intention for the videos to be passed forward for use by the forthcoming follow-up EU-FARMBOOK project (funded under Horizon Europe), in which it is anticipated that the number of views will increase significantly – thereby justifying the effort invested in their production.

